

Default Question Block

Introduction

This project is being conducted as part of CAUL's Advancing Open Scholarship program. The project is investigating current practice in Library support for Non-Traditional Research Outputs (NTROs), with a view to identifying areas where there are opportunities to improve or expand practice related to application of the FAIR principles to NTROs. The project will also explore how Indigenous knowledge principles should be applied to these outputs.

This survey is designed to gather information about university practices related to making NTROs FAIR and open across CAUL Member institutions. It also asks questions about key practice issues.

The survey calls for a single response from each CAUL Member institution (including CONZUL Members).

What we will do with the data

The information gathered from this survey will be used by the FAIR and Open Non-Traditional Research Outputs project team to develop a more detailed understanding of the role libraries can play in supporting researchers to make NTROs FAIR.

In any reports resulting from the survey, data will be reported in the aggregate and the names of institutions will not be linked with data. You will be asked to indicate which institution you are responding on behalf of to assist with

- identifying duplicate responses.
- to assist in follow up with libraries who have not yet responded.
- for possible reporting on broad categories of institution, eg group of eight, ATN network.

Some questions ask for a link to publicly accessible documents. We may refer to these documents in reporting findings, particularly to highlight examples of good practice.

Questions about the survey can be directed to Dr Gary Pearce at gary.pearce@rmit.edu.au

Thank you on behalf of the CAUL FAIR and Open Non-Traditional Research Outputs team for your participation in this survey.

Institutional details Institution: Dropdown

I have been nominated to provide the institutional response to this survey.

- Yes
- No

Institutional details

Consent to participate

By selecting yes below, you are indicating you consent to participate in the project are aware of

- how the data will be used
- have been nominated to provide a response to the survey on behalf of your institution.

- Yes, I consent
- No, I do not consent

Survey questions

To what extent are NTROs commonly recognised as legitimate research outputs at your university?

- Not legitimate
- Somewhat legitimate
- Moderately legitimate
- Very legitimate

Does your university mention NTROs in policies, statements of principles, procedures, or other guidance documents?

- Yes
- No

Please provide links to any publicly accessible documents that mention NTROs, or provide the name of the document if it is not publicly accessible.

Which of the following types of artifacts are treated as NTROs in your institution? Choose all that apply.

- Creative works
- Performance
- Recorded works
- Rendered works (eg digital copy of creative work)
- Curated exhibitions or events
- Research reports
- Portfolios
- Software
- Code
- Websites
- Databases
- Commissioned reports
- Other, please list

How are NTROs produced within the university published or otherwise made visible to external audiences?

Is there an emphasis within the university on making NTROs open access?

- Yes
 No

If yes, how is this emphasised? Eg in policy, through performance review, promotion criteria.

Does the university provide incentives to encourage researchers to make NTROs open access?

- Yes
 No

Please briefly describe these incentives and provide links to related policy or procedure if possible.

Is the library responsible for the collection of research outputs for the Excellence for Research in Australia (ERA) process at your university?

- Yes
 No

Does the library work with the university research office on any initiatives related to NTROs?

- Yes
 No

Please describe the initiatives and the library's role.

Does your library mention NTROs in policies, statements of principles, procedures, or other guidance documents?

- Yes
 No

Please provide links to any publicly accessible documents that mention NTROs, or provide the name of the document if it is not publicly accessible.

Does your library have guidelines that cover Indigenous knowledge issues that may be associated with regard to making NTROs FAIR and open?

- Yes
 No

What considerations are covered in these guidelines?

For the purpose of this survey, an institutional repository is defined as digital collections that capture, preserve and disseminate the research output of an institution.

In addition to traditional research outputs, which (if any) of the following are stored in your institution's institutional repository? Assume the broadest definition of NTRO. Select all that apply.

- Metadata-only entries for NTROs
 Born digital NTROs
 Digitised versions or recordings of NTROs that are not born digital
 Research data

Aside from the institutional repository, which of the following other repositories or systems does your institution have? Select all that apply.

- A separate repository containing metadata for NTROs
 A separate repository that stores born digital NTROs
 A separate repository that stores digitised versions or recordings of NTROs that are not born digital
 A separate repository for research data

- A separate repository for research software or code
- A system used to showcase NTROs (e.g. Omeka)

Does your institutional repository capture outputs other than theses and those that are assessable for ERA?

- Yes only those for ERA (apart from theses)
- No

Are NTROs that are not available open access archived in the institutional repository?

- Yes
- No

Does the institutional repository or any other repositories containing NTROs have an associated collection policy (or similar) that articulates what is collected in the repository?

- Yes
- No

If the policy is publicly available, please provide a link to the policy.

What research output categories are included in the policy?

What resource type categories does your Repository use in the collection and presentation of NTROs?

Please provide an estimate of the number of NTROs stored in your institution's repository/repositories.

Is the metadata used to describe NTROs in your institution's repository / repositories different from traditional research outputs?

- Yes
 No

To the best of your knowledge, please list the metadata elements that are used to describe NTROs.

Has your library adopted or adapted an existing schema for metadata for NTROs?

- Yes adopted
 Yes adapted
 No

Please indicate the schema you have adopted.

Please indicate the schema you have adapted.

Has your library created a schema for metadata for NTROs?

- Yes
 No

If this schema is publicly documented, please provide a link to the schema. If not, please describe briefly

Does the library provide support for researchers in the application of creative commons licenses for NTROs?

- Yes
 No

How does your library support or promote application of the FAIR principles to NTROs? For each of the areas below, indicate whether your library, promotes, provides advice, provides resources, provides training, or does the work on behalf of researchers.

	Promote	Provide advice	Provide resources (e.g. guides)	Provide training	Do it for them / on their behalf
Knowledge of FAIR principles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open access publishing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research profiles	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Licences and copyright	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Applying metadata in repositories	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI; use of, provision of)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Publication	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preservation of access	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Levels of access (e.g. restricted, embargos)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ensure NTROs are indexed in Google, Trove etc	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Which of the following present issues in supporting researchers to make NTROs FAIR and open? Select all that apply.

- NTROs often involve multiple items
- NTROs sometimes have associated documents describing and explaining the research content
- Combination of collaborative work and individual work
- The work may already be accessible online
- Quality of reproduction
- Capturing size and scale of the work
- Measuring impact
- Application of metadata standards
- Versions and iterations
- Archiving and long term preservation
- Physical nature of some research outputs
- Copyright
- Other, please list

Choose the three areas that represent the most significant issues in supporting researchers to make NTROs FAIR and open? Select three.

- NTROs often involve multiple items
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- Measuring impact
- Application of metadata standards
- Versions and iterations
- Archiving and long term preservation
- Physical nature of some research outputs
- Copyright
- Other

Please tell us about other things your library does to support researchers to make their NTROs FAIR and open.

Academics at my university require advice, support or training in the following areas:

- Application of metadata to their research outputs
- Use of persistent identifiers
- Preservation and archiving
- Copyright advice
- The application of NTROs to researcher profiles (eg ORCID)
- Evidencing the impact of their NTROs
- Support for publication and promotion of NTROs
- Assistance with development of research statements for NTROs
- Other (free text)

This project will develop a framework that provides guidance for CAUL Member institutions about how to increase the proportion of NTROs by Australian university researchers that are appropriately described, archived, preserved and made accessible.

How important is it that each of the following areas is addressed in the framework?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important
Dealing with multi-item NTROs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Assigning permanent unique identifiers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important
Capturing attributes (e.g. size, scale) of NTROs in either repositories or metadata	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dealing with NTROs that include a combination of collaborative and individual work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Measuring impact of NTROs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Evidencing the impact of NTROs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Metadata standards, including their application	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Managing versions and iterations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Dealing with work that is already available online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Long term preservation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Managing the physical nature of some outputs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Copyright	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Licencing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supporting sharing and reuse of NTROs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Supporting publication and promotion of NTROs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Populating ORCID profiles with NTROs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What other areas should be addressed in the framework?